

Factors Affecting Nursing Image in Eastern Province Hospitals, KSA

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Abstract

Background Nurses have been overlooked as autonomous healthcare providers due to an inaccurate image which projects them as caring and trusted, yet lacking in influence and autonomy. It is important for nurses to understand the image their profession wishes to convey, how the image falls short, and what can be done to improve it. **The aim** of this study was to explore responses of Nurse about factors affecting nursing's image. **Methods:** A study using survey questionnaires to assess factors affecting nursing's image. Descriptive statistics were used to analyze the data. Questions were analyzed using content analysis. **Result:** some of them concluded that low self-confidence (personal image) and lack of communication skills deeply affects the image of the nursing staff.

Keywords: Image, Nursing, factors affecting

Introduction

Current Image of Nursing and How It Is Impacted by Past Images: Nurses have struggled since ancient times to define the image of nursing and the professional role of the nurse. There are many different opinions about the nursing profession. Over the years the image of nursing evolves and changes, as nursing is promoted and seen as an independent profession that requires a high level of commitment, focus and dedication. Nursing in the modern era has many dimensions, around the definition of nursing as a profession. One of the continuing challenges in nursing is to enhance the public image and self-image of the nurse. The historical context of the nursing image goes back to Florence Nightingale, "Founder Nursing" Florence Nightingale is recognized as a nurse best known for her pioneering work during the Crimean War. She was also called "The Lady with the Lamp", as she was said to have made rounds of her

patients at night by the light of a lantern. International Nurses Day is celebrated every year on her birthday, May 12th. (Bostridge, 2008).

How Do Nurses View Themselves? The majority of nurses indicated that nurses have a number of roles that often depend on patient needs such as caregiver and decision maker, some nurses said that nurses also fulfill other professional roles for example, the nurse takes care of the patient, and provides health education to the families, in addition to this, the hospital directors also assign nurses to each position because they believe that the nurse can do everything. (Jones & Bartlett Learning, 2018)

The relationship between multiple generations of nurses: There is a gap between the new nurses (the boom generation) and the senior nurses (the traditional generation), and it may lead to the difficulty of exchanging knowledge and experiences between them. When some health organizations consider choosing a nurse they ask what generation or age groups are taken into consideration? What effect does this have on the nursing image? This means that the nursing picture is one of several age groups with different historical backgrounds. How can they both see nursing so differently. (Jones & Bartlett Learning, 2018)

How the media affects the image of nurses? The media is an important source of health information for the public. Therefore, the media has a significant impact on public perceptions of healthcare professionals and services and how coverage of health stories by the media affects the work of frontline

nursing staff. Nursing today suffers from many problems, including understaffing, poor working conditions and, in many places, inadequate pay for work skills and responsibility. All of these must be addressed. But improving people's view of the profession is one of the most important things. If nurses want to create a positive image of nursing in the media, should learn how to use the media to their advantage by making their voices heard regularly. It takes constant exposure to change the audience's perception. Nursing needs to control the image of the profession, If nurses have a more realistic image, it will be easier to support the types of services that nurses provide to the public. It would be easier to support an entry-level baccalaureate degree to provide the type of education required.

Assertiveness Assertive communications and assertive people are able to face problems in a constructive manner and are not silent. The image of the nursing profession has been influenced by the silence of nursing – Smith (1975) identified some critical rules of assertive behavior that can easily be applied to the difficulties nursing has had in changing its image and visibility and are still areas in need of improvement and remain relevant today. (Jones & Bartlett Learning, 2018)

Appearance and Professionalism: A matter of appearance and professionalism in nursing, first impressions are how patients form the opinions of their nurses. Occupation is influenced by many variables such as uniform, behavior, and image. The

purpose of this study was to explore perceptions of a nurse's appearance and expected professionalism, the research question was: Do nurses care about outward appearance? 84.2% of the answers confirm that appearance is very important for the nurse's image.

Self-esteem: Self-esteem is defined as a person's ability to be able to evaluate himself. Nurses with low self-esteem have great difficulties in communicating with colleagues and patients. Unlike nurses with high self-esteem, they have better cooperation with colleagues and patients and, therefore, better performance. at work.(safa,2018)

Description of the problem :When Author exposed to the clinical area; some issues were observed regarding the image of the nursing staff and how this could affect their dealings with patient. The image of nursing consists of not only their physical appearance but also the relationship with patients, colleagues and other healthcare professionals. Nursing staff's appearance (including grooming, personal hygiene) Communication skill problem with some staff that affects the patient care. Lack of confidence among

Years of experiences	1-5	5-10	10-20	>20
	28(10.8%)	67(25.8%)	93(35.8%)	72(27.7)

nursing staffs. Lack of teamwork. Lack of self-motivation which was due to low of self-esteem.

Methods: - descriptive cross sectional study was used aiming to assess factors affecting image of nursing professions. interview questionnaire and Observation of the nursing staffs in the clinical area
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regarding their appearance, style, and how they communicate. were used to collect quantitative data and qualitative data ,distributed to staff nurses in the clinical area. Sample of 260 randomly picked up nursing staffs to gain a deeper understanding of the impact of the nursing image on society Descriptive statistics were used to analyze the data. Questions were analyzed using content analysis.

RESULTS

Table (1) Gender and Age

Age	25-35	35-45	45-55
	74(28.5%)	95(36.5%)	91(35%)
Sex	M	F	
	41(15.8%)	219(89.2%)	

Table (2) Educational level

Education level	Diploma	BSN	MSN	PhD
	41(15.8)	180(69.2%)	38(14.61%)	1(0.4%)

Table (3) Years of experiences

Table (4) Factors Contributing to Nursing's Inconsistent Image

Factors	Frequency
Variety of education/credentials	120
Lack of professionalism	80

Image not a priority	70
Patients' personal experiences	38
Lack of leadership development	20
Gender role assumptions	40

Interview Process

Interviewed 260 staffs randomly from all hospital eastern province. Most staff concluded that Nursing is a respectable profession and they have expressed a level of control over how their image is portrayed. Conversely and some of them concluded that low self-confidence (personal image) and lack of communication skills deeply affects the image of the nursing staff. With this interview result,

Discussion

This research investigated the factors which promote an inconsistent image of the nursing profession, yes...psychological aspect of patients and their families are affected by the people who deal with them. Appearance plays a key and effective role in human life. The physical appearance and how nurses communicate with patients plays a vital role in providing better quality of patient care. Improving their image will eventually increase in their productivity and the performance of their job. First impression of how the employee dressed often builds relationship between him and his colleagues and those people who are dealing with them. Therefore, it is an

important aspect that affects the social and professional relationships. Physical appearance can leave a fantastic impression to others. Psychologist confirms that it is a mistake to ignore staff outward appearance because it affects their psychology in a very large extent. As a senior staff nurses, mentoring and coaching staff is part of our responsibility and we as a leader should act as a model.

Recommendation: Promote a positive image of nursing and demonstrate a significant contribution to society through the Nursing Image Improvement Project, demonstrating appropriate use of media coverage of the project or event. Educating the public about the professional roles in nursing and how these roles affect all individuals in their daily lives. Encouraging patients to share their experiences, both positive and negative, that deal with the nursing profession, to help the nursing community work to correct any problems. and support any achievements made by individuals and the profession.

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